

DISPUTE SETTLEMENT UNDERSTANDING: DEVELOPING A FIRM FOUNDATION FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF THE WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION

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I. INTRODUCTION

"One definition of peace is well-managed conflict . . . war is a very poor form of conflict management."² Well managed conflict alone is one reason for the existence of an entity like the World Trade Organization (WTO). The WTO's dispute settlement process is necessary to the protection of the global community's collective stake in world trade. Inefficiency, not to mention suffering and famine, can be a result of war. While postwar rebuilding can bring prosperity and national pride, it comes at a high price marked by lives lost, work that could have been accomplished, and sustainable development. In short, war constitutes a suboptimal solution to international problems.³

The "Rule of Law" assists in resolving international conflicts constructively because of its ability to reach and enforce peaceful settlements. If the rule of law enjoyed greater prevalence in the international arena, war would become only a distant and final means of resolution. In the case of Dispute Settlement Understandings (DSU), disputes are settled with multilateral negotiations, managed dispute settlements, and arbitrations as well as by other means. This article describes the DSU process in detail and provides an overview of important DSU Articles. Additionally, this article illustrates the process as it applies to a particu-

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2. HARLAN CLEVELAND, BIRTH OF A NEW WORLD, 77 (1993).

3. See CLEVELAND, *supra* note 2, at 64-89.

lar State while giving reference to that State's point of view.⁴ Finally, this article attempts to explore the global significance of the DSU.⁵

II. DSU PROCEDURE

The WTO promulgated the DSU while seeking to unequivocally set forth procedures the WTO would utilize in resolving disputes between member States. These twenty-seven articles of the DSU serve as the basis for dispute settlement in the WTO framework. The primary goal of the DSU is to "secure positive solutions to a dispute."⁶ The general goals of dispute resolution in the WTO system are set forth in Articles 1 through 3. In addition to the goals of the aforementioned articles, Articles 4 and 5 provide a framework for dispute settlement by making the DSU a forum for Member States to work out differences without having to result to more formalized court proceedings. Furthermore, Articles 6 through 16 add to the dispute settlement framework by providing the procedures for WTO dispute settlement panels, the body which initially reviews a case.

Additionally, Articles 16 and 17 set forth specific rules and procedures that specifically govern the actions and scope of the Appellate Body, or review board. Furthermore, Articles 19 through 25 expound the procedures for developing and adopting fair decisions. The above Articles contemplate how to implement panel decisions, which include how to develop and implement decisions, administer binding arbitration and deal with developing countries while pursuing the goal of strengthening the world system.⁷

4. See *infra* notes 127-177 (describing United States point of view in dispute with Japan over alcoholic beverage tariffs).

5. See *infra* notes 178-192.

6. GENERAL AGREEMENT ON TARIFFS AND TRADE: MULTILATERAL TRADE NEGOTIATIONS FINAL ACT EMBODYING THE RESULTS OF THE URUGUAY ROUND OF TRADE NEGOTIATION, Apr. 15, 1994 [FINAL ACT], ANNEX 2, UNDERSTANDING ON RULES AND PROCEDURES GOVERNING THE SETTLEMENT OF DISPUTES, 33 I.L.M. 1226, art. 3, para. 7 (1994) [hereinafter DSU].

7. See RALPH H. FOLSOM ET. AL., 1991 DOCUMENTS SUPPLEMENT TO INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS TRANSACTIONS 5 (2d. ed. 1991) (defining developing country). Folsom defines developing countries as "a broad range of countries that generally lack a high degree of industrialization, infrastructure and other capital investment, sophisticated technology, widespread literacy, and advanced

Finally, Article 27 discusses the Secretariat's role in the dispute settlement process.

A. Articles 1-3: Background and Context

Article 1 of the DSU provides the scope of the DSU's functions. Article 1 states that the DSU applies to "disputes between members concerning their rights and obligations" under the Agreement establishing the WTO, and various other covered agreements.⁸ Rules and procedures for specific treaties or agreements, however, may be expressly provided for in the treaty or agreement. In such situations, the specific rules and procedures of the particular agreement shall preempt conflicting DSU rules.⁹

Article 2 of the DSU creates the existence of the Dispute Settlement Board (DSB) that functions "to administer [the] rules and procedures" of the DSU.¹⁰ The DSU possesses a wide range of powers, including the ability to establish and "adopt panels and Appellate Body reports, maintain surveillance over adherence to these reports and authorize suspension of concessions."¹¹ Further, DSB influence may be exerted over the binding arbitration option of the DSU for implementation, because the arbitrator is often from the panel or Appellate Body which developed the relevant Appellate Report. Article 2 also mandates that the DSB make all decisions by consensus, meaning that generally, all members must agree to a decision.¹²

Article 3 sets forth the general provisions of the DSU and includes provisions for developing decisions of relative severity. Despite the relative severity of some of the decisions it is important to remember that "the aim of the dispute settlement mechanism is to secure a positive solution to a dispute."¹³ In keeping with the aims and goals of the DSU, Articles 4 and 5 provide for positive settle-

standards among their population as a whole." *Id.*

8. See generally Marrakesh Agreement Establishing the WTO, available in 33 I.L.M. 1141 (1994) [hereinafter WTO Agreement].

9. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 1.

10. See *id.* at art. 2, para. 1.

11. *Id.* at art. 2, para. 1.

12. See *id.* at art. 2., para. 4, n. 1.

13. *Id.* at art. 3, para. 7.

ment and reasoning for those mechanisms designed to encourage non-confrontational resolution.¹⁴ Article 3 provides for the "withdrawal of measures concerned if [such measures] are found to be inconsistent with GATT or . . . provisions of covered agreements."¹⁵ Additionally, Article 3 provides the injured State with a compensatory remedy if an impediment to trade cannot be removed; however, this is only a temporary remedy and will exist only until removal of impediment is possible. Finally, Article 3 will, when appropriate and upon the approval of a DSB, suspend the "application of concessions, or other obligations, under the covered agreements on a discriminatory basis vis-a-vis the other member."¹⁶

The DSU requires adherence to Articles XXII and XXIII of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trades (GATT).¹⁷ Additionally, Article 3 requires the DSU to develop decisions "in accordance with customary rules of interpretation of public international law."¹⁸ The DSU encourages prompt settlement of all disputes.¹⁹ Furthermore, the DSU requires that the DSU and other "covered agreements" must be adhered to and that no decision may impair benefits to any Member.²⁰ The DSU also emphasizes that engaging the dispute settlement process is not designed to be "contentious," and should not be interpreted as such.²¹ Additionally, the DSU mandates that Articles 4, 5, 6 and 12 may not be violated by decisions, even in decisions involving developing countries or least developed countries.²²

The WTO and the DSU recognize disputes that predate the establishment of the WTO are to be settled with the rules which were developed at the time the dispute originally occurred. Finally, Alternative Dispute Resolution

14. See DSU, *supra* note 6, arts. 3-4.

15. DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 3.

16. *Id.* at art. 3, para. 7.

17. October 30, 1947, 61 Stat. A-11, T.I.A.S. 1700, 55 U.N.T.S. 194 [hereinafter GATT].

18. DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 3, para. 2.

19. See *id.* at art. 21.

20. See *id.* at art. 3, para. 5.

21. See *id.* at art. 3, para. 10.

22. See *id.* at art. 3, para. 12.

(ADR) procedures are outlined for developing countries, and made available to them, pursuant to the WTO's Decision of April 5, 1966.²³ The ADR rules developed in Decision 5 may supersede part of the DSU. The precedence of ADR rules over DSU rules and procedures are important for the effective interpretation of rules that apply in various agreements. After setting forth the rules and procedures for the WTO's DSU settlement process, the DSU then discusses the first steps in the dispute settlement process which consists of consultation and retaliation.

B. Articles 4-5: Solutions without Formal Dispute Measures

Consultations are provided for in Article 4, and members agree to attempt to aid consultations in order to resolve the dispute at hand. The DSU allows a Member who may have violated a covered agreement to present its case. Response to a request for consultation should be made within ten days, and discussions should begin within thirty days after such a request.²⁴ If the respondent State fails to respond to a request for consultation, an applicant State may request a panel to resolve the dispute. Written requests for consultation, including notification of the complainant's issues and their legal basis, should be addressed to the DSB, to relevant Councils and Committees and to the respondent.²⁵ Within ten days of these written requests, a Member other than the consulting Members may request to be involved if they possess a "substantial trading interest" in consultations being held.²⁶ This becomes more evident where provisions of Article I of the GATT are implicated.

Article 4 consultations are confidential. A request for panel formation may be made sixty days after a request for consultation is received by the panel.²⁷ The consolidation process may be accelerated in cases of extreme urgen-

23. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 3, para. 12 (citing BISD 14/18).

24. See *id.* at art. 4, para. 3.

25. See *id.* at art. 4, para. 3.

26. See *id.* at art. 4, para. 4.

27. See *id.* at art. 4, para. 11.

cy, including those which involve perishable goods.²⁸ Additionally, the DSU pays "special attention" to the interests and protection of developing countries.²⁹

Furthermore, Article 5 provides "good offices" conciliation and mediation methods of dispute resolution. Article 5 resolution methods are voluntary and may be utilized by Member States before or during any phase of the DSU proceedings when the parties mutually agree to do so.³⁰ Further, the Director-General of the WTO may offer conciliation, mediation and good offices "with the view to assisting Members to settle a dispute."³¹ If these procedures are unsuccessful in developing a satisfactory agreement, then more formal action may be taken, as explained in the next section.

C. Articles 6-16: Panel Instructions

If the complaining party requests, the DSB will establish a panel at the first DSB meeting following the request unless the DSB unanimously determine consensus not to establish a panel.³² A request for a panel must be submitted in writing and must include a consultation summary, including the specific legal issues of the dispute as well as the basis for the applicant's complaint.³³ Additionally, the panel request should outline special requested terms of reference if anything other than the standard terms of reference are desired.³⁴

If the parties desire to utilize exceptional terms of reference, they must agree to such terms in writing.³⁵ Exceptional terms may be developed by the parties or the DSB may formulate a request which is subsequently drawn up by its chairman. Unless the parties reach an agreement to

28. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 4, paras. 8-9.

29. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 4, para. 10.

30. See *id.* at art. 5, para. 3.

31. *Id.* at art. 7.

32. See *id.* at art. 6, n.5. Footnote 5 to Article 6 provides in pertinent part: "if the complaining party so requests, a meeting of the DSB shall be convened . . . within 15 days of the request provided they at least 10 days in advance notice of the meeting is given." *Id.*

33. See *id.* at art. 6, para. 2.

34. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 6, para. 2.

35. See *id.* at art. 6, para. 2.

use exceptional terms, standard terms of reference are applied and are comprised of the following:

To examine, in the light of the relevant provisions in (name of the covered agreement(s) cited by the parties to the dispute), the matter referred to DSB by (name of party) in document . . . and to make such findings as will assist the DSB in making the recommendations or in giving the rulings provided for in that/those agreements.³⁶

Accordingly, panels should address relevant issues in covered agreements.³⁷ The provisions related to the Composition of Panels outlines the Member States to be included on a panel, and suggests panel's membership be comprised of individuals from government, business and industry who possess expertise and experience in international trade law and policy.³⁸ A "wide spectrum" of experience is to be drawn on in composing the dispute panel.³⁹ Additionally, panel members for a specific dispute may not be from one of the countries involved in the dispute, unless the parties otherwise agree.⁴⁰ The extensive list of available panelists includes governmental and non-governmental members, whose names are listed along with their individual areas of expertise. Generally, panels consist of three members; however, some instances the panel may consist of five members.⁴¹ Specific individuals will be

36. DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 7, para. 1.

37. *See id.* at art. 7.

38. *See id.* at art. 8, para. 1. Article 8 Paragraph 1 states in pertinent part: panels shall be comprised of well-qualified governmental and non-governmental individuals, including persons who have served on or presented a case to a panel, served as a representative of a Member or of a contracting party to GATT 1947 or as a representative to the Council or Committee of any covered agreement or its predecessor agreement, or in the Secretariat, taught or published on international trade law or policy, or served as a senior trade policy official of a Member.

Id.

39. *See id.* at art. 8, para. 2.

40. *See id.* at art. 8, para. 3.

41. *See* DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 8, para. 5 (stating panel consists of three members unless parties agree to five member panel). Paragraph 5 of Article 8 states in pertinent part: "Panels shall be composed of three panelists unless the parties to the dispute agree, within 10 days from the establishment of the

nominated by the Secretariat, and the parties "shall not oppose nominations except for [when there are] compelling reasons [for doing so]."⁴²

In the event no agreement is reached on panelists within twenty days of the establishment of panels, the Director-General of WTO, the Chairman of DSU and the Chairman of the relevant Council/Committee will appoint panelists.⁴³ All Member States shall undertake to allow officials from its government to serve as panelists, but such panelists do not serve in their official State capacity during the dispute settlement process and must remain neutral and unattached from their other governmental or organizational obligations.⁴⁴ Furthermore, the expenses encountered by a panelist in the execution of their duties will be met by WTO and not by the panelists or the Member State from which the panelist hails.⁴⁵ Finally, in a dispute between developed and developing Member States, the developing country may request that at least one panelist be from a developing country.⁴⁶

The DSU also provides for matter consolidation when more than one member requests a decision regarding the same matter. In such a case, the DSU will endeavor to consolidate the matter and have them adjudicated by a single panel.⁴⁷ If consolidation occurs, each Member may be present when any of the other members involved in the dispute makes arguments or receives a decision. Additionally, such decisions must protect the rights of all Members

panel, to a panel composed of five panelists. Members shall be informed promptly of the composition of the panel." *Id.*

42. H. H. Weiler & Eric Pan, Remarks at Seminar-Workshop on *The European Union, NAFTA and the WTO: Advanced Issues in Law and Policy* at Harvard Law School (May 1, 1997) (recognizing such activity as part Secretariat's unofficial powers). According to Weiler and Pan, if a decision is given that is not to the Secretariat's liking, the Secretariat may choose not re-appoint a panelist. *See id.* Additionally, Weiler and Pan recognize that an unqualified candidate would not be appointed by the Secretariat in the first place. *See id.*

43. *See DSU, supra* note 6, art. 8, para. 7.

44. *See id.* at art. 8, para. 9. Paragraph 9 of Article 8 also goes on to state that "members shall not give [panelists] instructions nor seek to influence them as individuals with regard to matters before a panel." *Id.*

45. *See id.* at art. 8, para. 11.

46. *See id.* at art. 8, para. 10.

47. *See id.* at art. 9, para. 1.

as though they were individual complainants.⁴⁸ If it is not feasible to combine panels, then the panelists from related disputes will be utilized in the disputes and the timing of the decisions will be harmonized.⁴⁹

Furthermore, the interests of third parties shall be protected during all proceedings. Any Member having notified the Panel of its third-party interest in a proceeding is allowed to be heard by the panel and to submit materials, which will be reflected in the panel report.⁵⁰ In addition, third parties will receive copies of all materials submitted to the panel by parties to the dispute. If a party were to decide, after the date for request has passed, that it should have been involved in the dispute settlement, then it may form a complaint,⁵¹ and the DSU will endeavor to have the same panelists preside over the matter.⁵²

Article 11 of the DSU sets forth the panel functions, and states that "the function of panels is to assist the DSB in discharging its responsibilities under [the DSU] and the covered agreements."⁵³ Throughout the dispute settlement process, the panel should also consult parties regularly to give them an opportunity to develop a "mutually satisfactory solution" to their dispute.⁵⁴ Panels shall follow working procedures from Appendix 3,⁵⁵ "unless the panel decides

48. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 9, para. 2.

49. See *id.* at art. 9, para. 3.

50. See *id.* at art. 10.

51. See *id.* at art. 10, para. 4 (stating that members may bring separate claims if they not party to current dispute procedure); see also Telephone Interview with Donald M. McRae, Professor of Law, University of Ottawa (May 1, 1997) [hereinafter McRae Interview]. McRae points out that Canada seriously considered pursuing action pertaining to the *Cuban Liberty and Solidarity Act* even though the United States and European Community have had the work of the panel suspended. See McRae Interview, *supra*.

52. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 10.

53. *Id.* at art. 11, para. 1.

54. See *id.* at art. 11, para. 2.

55. See FINAL ACT, *supra* note 6, APPENDIX 3, WORKING PROCEDURES, 33 I.L.M. 1245 (1994) [hereinafter WORKING PROCEDURES] (setting forth working procedures of DSU panels). The Working Procedures set forth the following rules:

2. The panel shall meet in a closed session. The parties to the dispute, and interested parties, shall be present at the meetings only when invited by the panel to appear before it.

3. The deliberations of the panel and the documents submitted to it shall be kept confidential. Nothing

otherwise after consulting the parties to the dispute."⁵⁶

Panel reports should allow sufficient time and procedural flexibility in order ensure the panels develop high-quality reports while not unduly delaying the process. Panels must

in this Understanding shall preclude a party to a dispute from disclosing statements of its own positions to the public. Members shall treat as confidential information submitted by another Member to the panel which that Member has designated as confidential. Where a party to a dispute submits a confidential version of its written submissions to the panel, it shall also, upon request of a Member, provide a non-confidential summary of the information contained in its submissions that could be disclosed to the public.

4. Before the first substantive meeting of the panel with the parties, the parties to the dispute shall transmit to the panel written submissions in which they present the facts of the case and their arguments.

5. At its first substantive meeting with the parties, the panel shall ask the party which has brought the complaint to present its case. Subsequently, and still at the same meeting, the party against which the complaint has been brought shall be asked to present its point of view.

6. All third parties which have notified their interest in the dispute to the DSB shall be invited in writing to present their views during a session of the first substantive meeting of the panel set aside for that purpose. All such third parties may be present during the entirety of this session.

7. Formal rebuttals shall be made at a second substantive meeting of the panel. The party complained against shall have the right to take the floor first to be followed by the complaining party. The parties shall submit, prior to that meeting, written rebuttals to the panel.

8. The panel may at any time put questions to the parties and ask them for explanations either in the course of a meeting with the parties or in writing.

9. The parties to the dispute and any third party invited to present its views in accordance with Article 10 shall make available to the panel a written version of their oral statements.

10. In the interest of full transparency, the presentations, rebuttals and statements referred to in paragraphs 5 to 9 shall be made in the presence of the descriptive part of the report and responses to questions put by the panel, shall be made available to the other party or parties.

11. Any additional procedures specific to the panel.

See id. at 1245-6.

56. DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 12, para. 1.

create a dispute resolution timetable within one week of their first consultation with the parties to the dispute.⁵⁷ Resolution timetables allow sufficient time for parties to submit materials and prepare for the dispute resolution process.⁵⁸ In addition, parties should adhere to and respect the specific deadlines set for the submission of written materials. Materials should be submitted to the Secretariat "for immediate transmission to the panel and [other parties] to the dispute."⁵⁹

While the Secretariat sets out the timetable for dispute resolution and the submission of materials, the Secretariat's discretion may present another potential source of unofficial influence in the DSU settlement regime. The system may be the subject of abuse because the Secretariat may choose to summarize the reports provided to them by the parties in a manner less complete than the way the parties presented the facts of the case to the panel, depending on the timetables utilized in the dispute resolution process.

The panel should submit full findings to DSB when the parties have not developed a mutually satisfactory solutions to their respective dispute. The DSU process should not take more than six months to complete. However, in instances of extreme urgency, the DSU procedure may be as short as three months long. Additionally, DSU proceedings may be extended to a period of nine months when reasons are supplied for an extension of the DSU proceedings. In addition to the panel's power to extend proceedings, the panel may also suspend work at any point if complainant so requests.⁶⁰ The suspension of the panel may last for up to twelve months, after which time the DSU panel loses its authority over the matter.⁶¹

57. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 12, para. 3.

58. See *id.* at art. 12, para. 4.

59. *Id.* at art. 12, para. 6.

60. See *id.* at art. 12, para. 12; see also generally *Concerning United States-The Cuban Liberty and Solidarity Act*, WT/DS38/5, available in 1997 WL 371060 (1997) [hereinafter *Cuban Liberty and Solidarity Act*] (illustrating situation where DSU panel has suspended work upon request of complainant). In *Cuban Liberty* the Chairman of the Panel stated: "the European Communities have requested the Panel to suspend the panel proceedings in accordance with Article 12.12 of the DSU." *Cuban Liberty and Solidarity Act, supra*.

61. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 12, para. 12.

A developing country may have exceptions made to the suspension rule in order to allow ample time to submit conclusions and arguments to the panel. Additionally, consultation extensions may be granted in the initial phases of the dispute resolution process solely where the party requesting the extension is a developing country. Furthermore, written accounts must be provided by the panel regarding what special considerations have been given to a developing country who is party to the dispute.⁶²

Information is given by request in virtually all circumstances.⁶³ However, in a case where the information agency is under the authority of a Member, the Member shall be notified first and confidential information need not be provided without written consent of that Member. Panels may seek information from any relevant source or expert. Additionally, the panels may convene an expert review group to review any technical or scientific issues involved.⁶⁴

The deliberation of a DSU panel is confidential and the reports of such panels are drafted in light of facts given by parties of the dispute. The deliberations occur, however, without the presence of the parties.⁶⁵ An individual panelist's opinions expressed in report must be anonymous.⁶⁶ Despite the panel Member's ability to make individual opinions, the panel must reach an unanimous opinion. The DSU's unanimity requirement is contrary to the United States Supreme Court system, which allows for justices to dissent in the Court's cases they do not believe properly reflect the legal precedent involved.

Following the consideration of rebuttal submission and oral arguments, the panel issues an interim decision and transmits it to the parties in order to receive comments from the parties to the dispute.⁶⁷ The interim decision also allows parties to the dispute to make final comments and make requests for clarification. In addition, such a

62. See *id.* at art. 12.

63. See *id.* at art. 13, para. 1.

64. See *id.* at art. 13, para. 2.

65. See *id.* at art. 14, paras. 1-2.

66. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 14, para. 3.

67. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 15, para. 1.

system allows the parties to further address specific issues and definitions to the panel before the report is circulated to the DSB for final disposition.⁶⁸ Upon receiving the decision, the parties may request an interim meeting at which time the parties will discuss the issues presented in the interim report.⁶⁹ Following the conclusion of such a meeting and other comments by the parties to the dispute, the DSU shall create a final report that includes all arguments made by the parties during interim review stage.⁷⁰

Members are sent reports and given twenty days to consider them before they are adopted by the DSU so they have time to contemplate the report.⁷¹ Members having objection to a report must circulate its reasons for objections to other Members ten days prior to the DSB meeting at which the report will be considered.⁷² Parties to the dispute "will have the right to participate fully" in this meeting in order to ensure their voices are heard by the DSB.⁷³ Within sixty days after circulation of a panel report to Members, the report will be adopted by the DSB, unless a party notifies of its intention to appeal the decision or if the DSB unanimously decides not to adopt the report. Nevertheless, Members maintain the right to comment and express their views on a panel report.⁷⁴

68. *See id.* at art. 15, para. 2.

69. *See id.* at art. 15, para. 2.

70. *See id.* at art. 15, para. 3 (stating that interim review stage must occur within Article 12 six month time period). Article 12 Paragraph 8 states in pertinent part:

In order to make the procedures more efficient, the period in which the panel shall conduct its examination, from the date that the composition and terms of reference of the panel have been agreed upon until the date the final report is issued to the parties to the dispute, shall, as a general rule, not exceed six months.

Id.

71. *See DSU, supra* note 6, art. 16, para. 1.

72. *See id.* at art. 16, para. 2.

73. *See id.* at art. 16, para. 3.

74. *See id.* at art. 16.

D. Articles 16-17: Appellate Body Procedures

A party to a dispute must formally notify the DSB of its decision to appeal.⁷⁵ The Appellate Body, established by the DSB consists of seven members, three of which may hear any given case. However, the three members who hear a specific dispute are determined by rotation. The DSB appoints the individuals who serve on the Appellate Body for four-year staggered terms. The members of the Appellate Body may be appointed for only one additional term.⁷⁶ All Members of the Appellate Body are recognized experts on international trade law and the various agreements covered by the DSU. These members are available at all times and must stay abreast of dispute settlement activities and relevant WTO activities.⁷⁷ Therefore, the appointment to a DSU Appellate Body amounts to part-time occupation.⁷⁸

"Only parties to the dispute, not third parties," have the option of appealing a decision. However, third parties may give written submissions to the Appellate Body for their consideration on appeal.⁷⁹ A report is generally issued in sixty days of receiving notice of appeal.⁸⁰ The scope of any appeal is limited to those issues covered in the panel report and the legal interpretations of the dispute developed by the panel.⁸¹ Additionally, much like the expenses of member panelists at the initial stage of the dispute settlement process, the expenses of the Appellate Body members are met by the WTO and not the individual or their country.⁸²

The DSU working procedures were developed by the Appellate Body with the assistance of the DSB Chairman

75. See *id.* at art. 16.

76. See McRae Interview, *supra* note 51. According to McRae, a list of names is submitted by governments for consideration, from which the WTO Directorate-General, DSB Chairman and the Chairman of Councils makes a decision on which candidate will comprise the Appellate Body. See *id.*

77. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 17.

78. See generally McRae Interview, *supra* note 51.

79. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 17, para. 4.

80. See *id.* at art. 17, para. 5.

81. See *id.* at art. 17, para. 6.

82. See *id.* at art. 17.

and Directorate-General.⁸³ Proceedings of the Appellate Body are confidential and the reports of the Appellate Bodies "are drafted without presence of the parties to the dispute and in light of the information provided."⁸⁴ Opinions expressed in the Appellate Body's report are anonymous and the Appellate Body addresses each of the issues that were raised through the panel during the Appellate Proceedings.⁸⁵

In developing decisions the Appellate Body may request a review by an expert panel even if the initial panel has relied solely on testimony from the involved parties. The Appellate Body has the power to "uphold, modify or reverse legal findings and conclusions of the panel."⁸⁶ Additionally, an appellate report "shall be adopted by the DSB and unconditionally accepted by the parties to the dispute," unless the DSB unanimously decides not to adopt the report within thirty days of the decision.⁸⁷

E. Articles 18-19: Procedural Instructions Applying to Panel and Appellate Body

The DSU rules forbid the parties from making any *ex parte* communications with the panel or the Appellate Body regarding matters under their consideration.⁸⁸ Written submissions to the panel are confidential, but shall be made available to the other parties. However, nothing in the DSU rules prevent a party from disclosing its position to the public.⁸⁹ Additionally, if a nonparty Member requests a nonconfidential summary of written submissions they shall be provided with such summaries by both parties which is suitable for public disclosure.⁹⁰

A panel or Appellate Body, in finding that a Member undertakes conduct that does not conform with covered agreements will instruct that Member to bring such actions

83. See *id.* at art. 17, para. 9.

84. DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 17, para. 10.

85. See *id.* at art. 17, para. 11.

86. *Id.* at art. 17, para 12.

87. See *id.* at art. 17.

88. See *id.* at art. 18, para. 1.

89. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 18, para. 1.

90. See *id.* at art. 18.

into compliance with the agreements.⁹¹ Additionally, governing body may also suggest ways for the violating Member to accomplish such compliance.⁹² Neither body, however, may diminish rights or obligations provided for in covered agreements, as stated in Article 3 of the DSU.⁹³

F. Articles 20-25: Final Reports and Implementation

Articles 20 through 25 set forth how final reports given to the DSB are adopted and implemented. Except under special circumstances of extended Appellate review, the time from which the DSB first establishes the panel to the time it hears the final decision for adoption cannot exceed nine months.⁹⁴ If the case is appealed, then a twelve month time limitation for dispute settlement is allowed.⁹⁵ In general, prompt compliance with recommendations and rulings is necessary, with special attention being paid to matters concerning developing countries.⁹⁶ The concerned Member is required to inform the DSB the steps it will take to comply at a meeting which is held within thirty days after the report is adopted.⁹⁷ If the member cannot comply immediately, then it will have a "reasonable period" of time in which to bring their actions into compliance.⁹⁸

91. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 19, para. 1.

92. See *id.* at art. 19, para. 1.

93. See *id.* at art. 19, para. 2.

94. See *id.* at art. 20.

95. See *id.* at art. 20.

96. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 21, paras. 1-2.

97. See *id.* at art. 21, para. 3.

98. See *id.* at art. 21, para. 3(a)-(c) (setting forth elements utilized in determining reasonable time). Article 21 of the DSU states that reasonable time may be determined by:

(a) the period of time proposed by the Member concerned, provided that such period is approved by the DSB; or, in the absence of such approval;

(b) a period of time mutually agreed by the parties to the dispute within 45 days after the date of adoption of the recommendations and rulings; or, in the absence of such agreement,

(c) a period of time determined through binding arbitration within 90 days after the date of adoption of the recommendations and rulings . . .

The DSU gives the arbitrator fifteen months to implement the decision; however, a longer or shorter period of time may be utilized depending upon the "particular circumstances" of the dispute.⁹⁹ Generally, this reasonable period of time shall be determined within fifteen months of the initial panel establishment by the DSB, or, in exceptional circumstances, within eighteen months of the initial panel establishment. If the recommended compliance is inconsistent with the covered agreements, then the original panel will review the compliance measures taken within ninety days of the decision.¹⁰⁰ Implementation of the recommendation by the involved Member will be monitored by the "involved Member providing a report on implementation ten days before each DSB meeting; [by the member] formally [appearing] on DSB agenda six months following establishment of reasonable time period; [and] a Member may request progress report at any time."¹⁰¹

Additionally, if a Member developing country raises an issue, then the DSB shall consider taking further action that is "appropriate to the circumstances" and that takes into account trade coverage issues as well as the "impact on the economy of [the] developing country Members concerned."¹⁰²

Compensation and suspension of concessions constitute temporary alternatives that are available if the Member does not comply with the ruling, though compliance with the ruling is preferred to either of these options. In case implementation does not occur within decided time period, negotiations will occur between involved Members. If negotiations fail, any party having invoked the dispute settlement procedure "may request authorization from the DSB to suspend the application to the Member concerned of concessions or other obligations under the covered agreements."¹⁰³ In considering which concessions will be suspended, the DSU utilizes certain guidelines.¹⁰⁴

99. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 21, para. 4.

100. See *id.* at art. 21, para. 5.

101. See *id.* at art. 21.

102. *Id.* at art. 21.

103. DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 22, para. 2.

104. See *id.* at art. 22. Article 22 delineates between same sector and different sector suspensions. See *id.* at art. 22, para. 3 (b)(c). Section 3(b) states

The level of suspension or concessions the DSB authorizes is equivalent to those rights the Member has impaired. Even equivalent concessions may not be authorized if prohibited by a specific covered agreement.¹⁰⁵ At times, the DSB will grant opportunities for member to suspend concessions within thirty days after a reasonable time period. In cases where a Member objects, however, the DSU will not suspend concessions while arbitration is carried out.

Arbitration will be under an individual or group consisting of the original panel if they are available; however, if they are not available the arbitrator will be appointed by the Director-General.¹⁰⁶ This arbitrator will determine whether the proposed suspensions are equivalent to level of nullification or impairment, as well as whether suspensions are allowed under the covered agreement.¹⁰⁷ This arbitrator's decision is final, and a party may not seek a

that "if [a] party considers it is not practicable to suspend concessions or other obligations with respect to the same sector(s), it may seek to suspend concessions or other obligations in other sectors under the same agreement." *Id.* art. 22, para. 3(b). Section 3(c) states that "if [a] party considers that it is not practicable or effective to suspend concessions or other obligations with respect to other sectors under the same agreement, and that the circumstances are serious enough, it may seek to suspend concessions or other obligations under another covered agreement." *Id.* at art. 22, para. 3(c).

For the purposes of Article 22, "sector" means:

- (i) with respect to goods, all goods;
- (ii) with respect to services, a principal sector as identified in the current 'Services Sectoral Classification List' which identifies such sectors;
- (iii) with respect to trade-related intellectual property rights, each of the categories of intellectual property rights covered in Section 1 [-] 7 of Part II, or the obligations under Part III, or Part IV of the Agreement on TRIPS.

DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 22, para. 3(f)(i)-(iii).

For the purposes of Article 22, "agreement" means:

- (i) with respect to goods, the agreements listed in Annex 1A of the WTO Agreement, taken as a whole as well as the Plurilateral Trade Agreement in so far as the relevant parties to the dispute are parties to these agreements;
- (ii) with respect to services, the GATS;
- (iii) with respect to intellectual property rights, the Agreement on TRIPS.

Id. at art. 22, para. 3(g)(i)-(iii).

105. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 22, paras. 4-5.

106. See *id.* at art. 22, para. 6.

107. See *id.* at art. 22, para. 7.

second arbitration decision. Suspension will occur only until the time when said Member has complied, and surveillance pursuant to Article 21 will apply.¹⁰⁸ Members will take reasonable steps to insure compliance, even at the local level, and if implementation cannot be secured at the local level, then suspension of compensation or other obligations will apply.¹⁰⁹

Members shall abide by the DSU and not take the unilateral action of suspension against other Members; this is very important for strengthening the multilateral system.¹¹⁰ The DSU will not make a determination that a violation has occurred, or that any infringement has occurred, except through the DSB and consistent with the reports adopted by the DSB.¹¹¹ Procedures must be followed in determining actions for the level of suspension or the time allowed for other Members to follow recommendations.¹¹²

"Particular consideration" will be given to individual situations when enforcing decisions against least developed countries (LDC's), including "exercising due restraint in raising matters. . . in asking for compensation or concessions by these members."¹¹³ When a satisfactory initial agreement has not been reached, efforts will be made by the Directorate-General and Chairman of DSB to reach such an agreement before the panel request is made such actions will include "good offices," conciliation and mediation.¹¹⁴

Arbitration occurs when no agreement for an implementation time plan can be reached within ninety days of the time the ruling is adopted by the DSB. A general implementation guideline for arbitration to follow, in terms of decisions for implementation time period, is fifteen months.¹¹⁵ Articles 21 and 22, in fact, apply *mutatis mutandis* to arbitration awards.¹¹⁶ Expeditious arbitration is

108. See *id.* at art. 22, para. 8.

109. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 22., para. 9.

110. See *id.* at art. 23, para. 6.

111. See *id.* at art. 23, para. 2(a).

112. See *id.* at art. 23.

113. *Id.* at art. 24, para. 1.

114. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 24.

115. See *id.* at art. 21., para. 4.

116. See *id.* at art. 25, para. 4.

designed as a helpful means of alternative dispute resolution. Resort to arbitration shall occur at the mutual consent of the parties, and such agreement must be transmitted to all members before the arbitration process commences.¹¹⁷ "Other members may become party to the arbitration proceeding only at the agreement of parties involved."¹¹⁸ Parties involved shall comply with the ruling. Arbitration awards will be notified by the DSB and the relevant Council or Committee, where any Member may raise relevant points.¹¹⁹

G. Article 26: Article XXIII GATT 1994 Complaints

The panel and the Appellate Body decisions are designed for cases where a covered agreement is violated, and detailed justification is therefore required for any involvement otherwise. If effects of other measures result in the impairment of benefits without violating a covered agreement, as outlined in Article XXXIII paragraph 1(b) of the GATT, then the DSB suggestions and non-binding arbitration are available to rectify the situation.¹²⁰ In the case of violation under paragraph 1(c), when 1(a) and 1(b) do not apply, the situation will be heard and decided by the DSU, but Members must be especially well-informed of the proceedings for such resolution proceedings to continue.¹²¹ The decision of April 12, 1989 shall apply to adoption consideration and surveillance of consideration.¹²² Further, panels shall deal with this violation separately from those involving other paragraphs.

H. Article 27: Official Secretariat Role In Judicial System

The World Trade Organization Secretariat will assist panels,¹²³ "by providing legal, historical and procedural as-

117. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 25, para. 2.

118. *Id.* at art. 25, para. 2.

119. See *id.* at art. 25., para. 3.

120. See *id.* at art. 26, para. 1.

121. See *id.* at art. 26, para. 2.

122. See *id.* at art. 26, para. 2.

123. See Renato Ruggiero, "Swearing-in Ceremony of Appellate Body Members Completes Institutional Structure of WTO- Says Director -General Renato Ruggiero." Press Release No. 32. World Trade Organization. Dec. 3, 1995,

pects of matters dealt with, and providing technical and secretarial and technical support."¹²⁴ The Secretariat may provide a form of "legal aid" to developing countries by making available a legal expert from the WTO, which also serves to allow the Secretariat to remain impartial.¹²⁵ Further, the Secretariat will conduct special training courses for Members regarding procedures to allow countries' experts to be better informed.¹²⁶

III. UNITED STATES: ENGAGING JAPAN OVER DOMESTIC DIFFERENTIAL TAXATION ON LIQUOR

The United States (U.S.), a developed country, and Japan, also a developed country, conduct significant trade with one another. One item where contention has existed between the two countries is over liquor trade. Under a covered agreement brought into the WTO, the United States believed that Japan had tariffs which were preferential to Japanese goods and were not in accordance with these agreements. The U.S. believed that there was a differential tax on nearly identical products. The U.S. maintained that such like-products should have been taxed equally, under Article III Section 2 of the GATT which requires a Member State to treat products from other countries the same as they treat their own nationally made products.¹²⁷

In relation to this issue, the U.S. was first obligated to exercise its judgment in deciding "whether to pursue action under [the dispute settlement] procedures would be fruitful."¹²⁸ The U.S. sought equalized tariffs under GATT Article III Section 2 or some similar structure.¹²⁹ The

<<http://www.wto.org/WTO/French/Pressf/Press37f.htm>> (last visited Apr. 28, 1997). Ruggiero states that major assistance, however, is not given to the Appellate Board. *See id.* The Appellate Board, however, maintains its own Secretariat, which is necessary to maintain impartiality and independence from the WTO-at-large. *See id.* According to Ruggiero, this independence is necessary. *See id.*

124. DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 27, para. 1.

125. *See id.* at art. 27, para. 2.

126. *See id.* at art. 27, para. 3.

127. *See* GATT, *supra* note 17, art. III, § 2 (expounding GATT concept of national treatment).

128. DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 3, para. 7.

129. *See Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS8/R, WT/DS10/R,

U.S.'s desire to equalize tariffs was consistent with the aim of the DSU which seeks to secure a solution acceptable to both parties, and, in absence of this, "to first secure the withdrawal of the measures concerned if [such measures] are found to be inconsistent with the provisions of a covered agreement."¹³⁰ Consequently, the DSU decided to move forward with the proceedings.

The following recounts the relevant steps the U.S. took in the DSU process and details the conduct of the U.S. engaging this process. The US took this case through the full dispute settlement process from initial consultations through final arbitration.¹³¹ Additionally, the following illustrates how the US initiated the DSU procedure against Japan, requested a panel, went through the appeal process and gained a final decision on implementation by arbitration.

A. Consultations

The initial step in the dispute settlement process is for a Member to engage in consultations. During this time, "sympathetic considerations" are given by each party involved, and the parties "attempt to obtain satisfactory adjustment" of the matters raised. All of these consultations are kept confidential.¹³² In the case on *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*,¹³³ the US recognized that the European Community had requested consultations with Japan on its taxes on alcoholic beverages on June 21, 1995. The U.S., who also had an interest in this matter, requested consultations under the aforementioned Article XXIII of GATT on July 7th, 1995. The U.S. consultations also regarded the tariffs imposed by Japan's internal liquor law. On July 20, 1995, the U.S. engaged in consultations with

WT/DS11, para. 3.3, available in 1996 WL 406720 (July 11, 1996) (explaining U.S. requested panel find Japanese alcohol import tax inconsistent with GATT art. III:2).

130. DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 3, para. 7.

131. See *The Panel Process* <<http://www.wto.org/wto/about/dispute2.htm>> (last visited Feb. 24, 1999) (detailing DSU procedure).

132. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 4, paras. 2, 5-6.

133. WT/DS8/R, WT/DS10/R, WT/DS11/R, para. 3.3, available in 1996 WL 406720 (July 11, 1996).

Japan simultaneously with the other complainants, the European Community and Canada. On July 21, the US also engaged in bilateral consultations with Japan regarding provisions under Article XXIII Section 1. Japan and the US could not reach acceptable solutions were not found to matters raised.¹³⁴ In order to maintain the confidentiality of the process, the DSB will not make the proceedings of the consultations public.¹³⁵

B. Panel

A Member to a dispute may request establishment of a panel, and must make their request in writing which briefly states that consultations were held, as well as stating the legal basis for the case.¹³⁶ If multiple complaints are involved, then the Member should anticipate consolidation of complaints to one panel, though the Member should be prepared to submit its own individual arguments because each party is vested with individual rights and may present separate arguments.¹³⁷

The panel must then quickly set a timetable for the resolution of the dispute, including the dates by which ma-

134. See *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS8/R, WT/DS10/R, WT/DS11/R, para. 1.1-1.4, available in 1996 WL 406720 (July 11, 1996).

135. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 4, para. 6. The confidentiality of the consultation process does make it somewhat difficult to recreate objectively what occurred in the proceedings. In order to analyze what happened, the public is only left with individual interpretations from parties involved without a single agreed-upon statement of proceedings. This brings the transparency issue to light in that agreements may not be analyzed by the public outside the DSB, and whether other countries' interests are truly considered when a dispute is settled.

Consider the possibility that a settlement had been reached whereby a type of alcohol exported by another party had been left out of the agreement. This could make more difficult the issues surrounding:

1) Actually insuring that the inappropriate law is repealed, rather than simply settling on a mutually agreeable course of action under which the law would still remain.

2) Specifically to this case, being sure that liquors which should be included under the law, even those not specifically mentioned in the matter at hand, are addressed.

These issues suggest the need for an especially vigilant DSB in terms of being sure that settlements do not impair benefits or concessions made to other members. This could be accomplished by, perhaps, having an implementation report on laws changed based on consultations being presented to the DSB.

136. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 6, paras. 1-2.

137. See *id.* at art. 9, paras. 1-2.

terials must be received. This process should not exceed six months, but may be extended to up to nine months. After the DSB sets the time-table, the Members must submit written arguments to the Secretariat for "transmission" to the panel. The Members involved will then make arguments before the panel and, at a second session, the Members may make rebuttal arguments. The Members may release their own views to the public, as well as a non-confidential version of views of all parties, although panel deliberations must remain confidential.¹³⁸

The panel must then reach an interim decision. The Members may submit comments and requests for a meeting as well as clarifications regarding issues raised and decided in the interim report at this point. The review process must also occur within the six month time limit required for a panel to make a decision.¹³⁹ Following this meeting, panel deliberations must occur and a final panel report must be issued to the parties.

If the panel's report is not appealed, then the report will go before the DSB for adoption. Members may expect the report to be adopted by the DSB within sixty days from the date of the report's submission. The Members may participate actively in the DSB adoption hearing.¹⁴⁰

On September 14, 1995, the U.S. requested the establishment of a panel with normal terms of reference. This decision by the US was wise because had they instead submitted as an "interested third party," they would not have been allowed to appeal the panel decision because they would not have been directly involved in the process. Further, if the U.S. had signed on as a third party, it is unlikely that they would have maintained such an active role in the arbitration proceedings.

The European Community and Canada also requested a panel on the same day, which was within the sixty day requirement from time consultations were requested by the parties. The U.S., European Community and Canadian complaints were consolidated pursuant to Article 9 of the

138. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 12, paras. 1, 3, 6, 8-9.

139. See *id.* at art. 15.

140. See *id.* at art. 16, paras. 3-4.

DSU, and one three-member panel was established to hear the claims on October 30th.¹⁴¹ Facts were submitted and then accepted, including the types of alcohol involved in the dispute (Shochu-Types A and B, whisky/brandy, spirits and liqueurs) and the taxes imposed on them.¹⁴² It was also established that the 1987 *Panel Report on Japan-Custom Duties, Taxes and Labeling Practices on Imported Wines and Alcoholic Beverages*,¹⁴³ (1987 GATT panel) had been decided against Japan on a separate alcohol-tax issue, and Japan had implemented some recommended measures by 1989.¹⁴⁴

At this point the U.S. made arguments. The U.S. claimed that the Japanese tax system for alcohol was illegal because it violated Article III Section 2 of the GATT. The U.S. claimed that all "brown spirits" and "white spirits" are "like products." In absence of this ruling, the U.S. requested that "white spirits" are "like spirits" and that "brown spirits" are "directly competitive and substitutable." In either case, repeal of the Liquor Tax Law was requested. The U.S. cited the 1992 case, *United States-Taxes Affecting Alcoholic and Malt Beverages*,¹⁴⁵ as an example of where a differential tax system was not allowed to aid smaller producers in an effort to adjust to tax changes.¹⁴⁶ This would suggest necessary repeal of the Liquor Tax law. Japan responded that the U.S. had not been specific in raising this issue, and more importantly the U.S. had not raised this issue during consultations, bringing it out of scope for a panel decision.¹⁴⁷

The U.S. argued that the 1987 GATT panel, which provided many distinctions necessary for the case at hand, should be used as guidance for determination of "like" and

141. See *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS8/R, WT/DS10/R, WT/DS11/R, paras. 1.8, 1.10-1.11, available in 1996 WL 406720 (July 11, 1996).

142. See *id.*, paras. 2.1-2.4.

143. L/6216-34S/83, available in 1987 WL 421964 (October 13, 1987).

144. See *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS8/R, WT/DS10/R, WT/DS11/R, paras. 2.5-2.8, available in 1996 WL 406720 (July 11, 1996).

145. DS23/R-39S/206, 1992 WL 799397 (Mar. 16, 1992).

146. See *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS8/R, WT/DS10/R, WT/DS11/R, para. 4.2, 1996 WL 406720 (July 11, 1996).

147. *Id.* at para. 4.3.

"competitive and substitutable" products but not as a binding factor. In essence, the GATT 1987 panel stated it "would be unnecessary for the panel to find that GATT 1947 Panel Reports are just as binding as the text of GATT 1994 itself," and pointed to "far-reaching and unpredictable consequences."¹⁴⁸

Japan responded that the 1987 GATT panel should not guide the proceedings because it provided "limited precedential value," to the procedure and even the GATT recognized its limited value when it stated that "the panel would take into account the 1980 panel report, but . . . did not feel that it was legally bound to follow it."¹⁴⁹ The *Japan-Taxes* panel stated, therefore, it would "take into account the 1980 panel report and the legitimate expectations created by its adoption, but also other circumstances of this complaint."¹⁵⁰ Moreover, Japan argued that the circumstances were different because the tax law involved in 1987 GATT panel was changed, and specific facts regarding the 1987 decision would, therefore, be misleading.¹⁵¹ Also, Japan argued for the application of the "Aim and Effect" test proposed by the U.S., and cited the standard set in the 1992 panel decision entitled *United States-Taxes Affecting Alcoholic and Malt Beverages* as precedent.¹⁵²

On May 20, 1996, the interim report was issued to the parties, and on May 28, 1996, the U.S. requested to review issues with the panel, pursuant to DSU Article 15, paragraph 2. The U.S. submitted press reports regarding the results of the interim review, but agreed to adhere to a panel's confidentiality because they wanted to ensure the "credibility of the system."¹⁵³ The U.S. argued that adopted reports should not constitute "subsequent practice" found in Article 31 of the Vienna Convention on the Law

148. *Id.* at para. 4.7.

149. *European Economic Community-Restrictions on Imports of Dessert Apples-Complaint by Chile*, L/6491-36S/93, available in 1989 WL 587605 (Apr. 18, 1989).

150. *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS8/R, WT/DS10/R, WT/DS11, para. 4.8, available in 1996 WL 406720 (July 11, 1996).

151. *See id.* at paras. 4.8, 4.10.

152. *See id.* at para. 4.9.

153. *See id.* at para. 5.3.

of the Treaties (Vienna Convention),¹⁵⁴ but the panel maintained its decision that adopted reports do constitute subsequent practice. The U.S. argued, in concert with Japan, that the "aim and effect" test should hold, particularly because GATT Article III Section 2 took its meaning from GATT Article III Section 1. However, the panel also rejected this argument.

The U.S. then requested that a definition be developed for "dissimilar taxation," and one was added into the decision. The U.S. argued for a more specific legal test, particularly a test, for "directly competitive or substitutable products," but the panel said the test had been established by previous panels, and that the marketplace would be a specific determinant.¹⁵⁵ Accordingly, the United States did receive some benefits from this section, including clarifications of the requested definitions. At the same time, major procedural tests remained unchanged. However, change did occur during the Appellate Body review. It is interesting to note that this panel review may serve as a forum for raising issues that a party wishes to look at in the Appellate Body review. This is especially important, because issues which are clearly raised during the panel are ones which are addressed during the Appellate Body review.

The panel's findings were received on July 11, 1996. The panel first stated that its terms of reference did not permit it to entertain the claims of the U.S. regarding the Japanese Taxation Special Measures Law.¹⁵⁶ It then determined that the Japanese Liquor Tax Law is inconsistent with GATT Article III Section 2. Contrary to U.S. claims, the panel decided that the Vienna Convention Articles 31 and 32 did apply to this dispute established they would apply "subsequent practice" with respect to the 1987 GATT panel because of the decision of contracting parties to adopt the decision.¹⁵⁷ Such an outcome could actually

154. 1155 U.N.T.S. 331, U.N. Doc. A/Conf. 39/27 (1969) [hereinafter Vienna Convention].

155. See *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS8/R, WT/DS10/R, WT/DS11, paras. 5.3-5.4, 5.10, 5.12, available in 1996 WL 406720 (July 11, 1996).

156. See *id.* at para. 6.5.

157. See *id.* at paras. 6.7-6.10.

be viewed as establishing a form of customary international law similar to common law, which, if not overturned, would allow preceding cases to be binding on future disputes. However, since the Appellate Body did not maintain this decision, the desired presence of international customary law in this area never came to bear.

Based on the wording of the GATT Article III Section 2, the U.S. claimed that an "aim and effect" test is required to determine whether a country's laws violate the national treatment standard. The panel, however, stated that this test, is based in the "so as to afford protection" clause of Article III Section 2. Further, it stated the aim was often indiscernible, and the only precedent given for this case was found in the case concerning the *United States-Taxes on Automobiles*,¹⁵⁸ which the DSU never adopted.¹⁵⁹ An adopted panel allows a measure of adoption by the contracting parties. This is a point on which the Appellate Body concurred and suggests the legitimacy of this argument and its availability for reference in future cases. Without such an adoption, the panel decisions merely serve as recommendations and do not provide a bases for subsequent action.

The test for determining whether items constitute "like products" includes the end-use and similar composition, as well as a measure of what is found in the marketplace. Further, whether products are competitive and substitutable depends on whether they possess the same characteristics. The U.S. submitted arguments undermining Japan's two studies regarding differences between shochu and the other alcohol forms. The Panel agreed with the United States on this matter. It is interesting to note that the panel could have called for separate studies to be performed in a more objective and meaningful manner, but the panel relied on its own conclusions about this, as well as basing it on past data from the removal of taxes. The panel's conduct was bold in that they were able to discern what constituted a valid test of the market, because debate still exists about

158. DS31/R, available in 1994 WL 910937 (Oct. 11, 1994).

159. See *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS8/R, WT/DS10/R, WT/DS11/R, paras. 6.17-6.18, available in 1996 WL 406720 (July 11, 1996).

valid tests of the market in general and who performs them well. Perhaps calling an expert for determination would have been a prudent action; otherwise this would add two dimensions to the qualifications of the panelists and Appellate Body members: economist and tax attorney. The lack of the utilization of the ASI test also has important ramifications on determinations. Ultimately, a remedy was necessary because taxes constituted more than a mere *de minimis* difference.¹⁶⁰

The Panel decided that shochu and vodka constituted "like products," and the taxes comprised of more than a *de minimis* tax differential and made the Japanese laws violative of the first sentence of Article III Section 2 of the GATT. Additionally, the WTO panel determined that Shochu, whisky, brandy, rum, gin, genever and liqueurs constituted "directly competitive and substitutable" products which Japan did not tax similarly, and such dissimilar treatment violated the second sentence of Article III Section 2. Therefore, the WTO panel recommended Japan bring their laws into conformity with the national treatment standard of the GATT.¹⁶¹ Additionally, the United States appealed based on the procedural tests applied, while Japan appealed the decision because the panel's final decision and the procedural tests applied by the panel.

C. Appellate Body

A three-member group from the Appellate Body considers the report by the Panel and decides whether to uphold or to overturn all or part of it.¹⁶² The Appellate Body may also conduct a separate investigation, including establishing a separate panel of technical experts, if it so wishes.¹⁶³ Third parties may not appeal, and the Appellate Body must receive submissions from all interested third parties, but will not hear any oral arguments from third parties. The DSB and the parties involved, upon receiving recommendation from the Appellate Body, will uncondi-

160. See *id.* at paras. 6.29-6.33.

161. See *id.* at para. 7.1.

162. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 17, para. 1.13.

163. See generally McRae Interview, *supra* note 33.

tionally accept the report by consensus. All Appellate Body proceedings are confidential, though non-confidential versions of Member views on issues may be distributed to the public. Decisions shall generally be rendered within sixty days of the notice of appeal and cannot exceed ninety days.¹⁶⁴

The United States appealed and performed Appellant submission on August 23, 1996, while giving Appellee submission on September 2, 1996.¹⁶⁵ Accordingly, the United States and Japan were in the curious position of being both Appellant and Appellee for this section. It is also interesting in that the U.S. and Japan agreed on one matter being appealed, the procedural test, while both countries wanted different outcomes from this test. The U.S. demanded no further concessions, and was therefore risking (on legal principal) a change of the test which had the potential to result in a less favorable recommendation by the Appellate Body than that handed down by the DSU. Further, the U.S., who "won" this case, had more issues raised before the Appellate Body.¹⁶⁶ It is interesting that the system was flexible enough to accommodate such paradoxes. The Appellate Body came to the same decisions as the panel. It upheld the panel's conclusions as well as their recommendations.¹⁶⁷ Several procedural revisions requested by the U.S. were nevertheless examined, and in some cases the corresponding panel decisions were overturned.

The U.S. requested the Appellate Body overturn the panel's interpretation of the power of adopted panel reports. The Appellate Body did overturn the panel's interpretation of adopted panel reports in favor of affording them less authority, while also upholding the panel decision regarding lack of authority of unadopted panels. The Appellate Body stated that because the Ministerial Conference has final power and because no part of the GATT 1947 or

164. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 17, paras. 4-5, 9-11.

165. See *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS11/AB/R, sec. C., available in 1996 WL 738800, (Oct. 4, 1996).

166. See *id.*, at sec. C, para. 2 (outlining that US had raised one more issue on appeal than Japan).

167. See *id.* at sec. A.

1994 can be nullified by panel decisions, it did not agree that "subsequent practice" is established through reports adopted by agents of the contracting parties. Therefore, such agreements did not constitute a binding "subsequent agreement" in the sense of Article 31 of the Vienna Convention.

Nevertheless, adopted panels "are considered part of the GATT *acquis* and "create legitimate expectations among WTO Members and . . . should be taken into account when they are relevant to a dispute."¹⁶⁸ In other words, when they apply, they should be used if possible because of the expectation of this usage is an expectation created by adoption. This could be construed as a potential passage to common law. A *de facto* obligation to use past panels as *stare decisis* when looking into matters could evolve into the formation of a consistent system of international law in trade disputes taking place under the WTO's DSU regime. The evolution of international *stare decisis* would occur over time, as enough decisions are made and as those decisions begin to fill a wide enough range of matters that would be covered in any given dispute. In other words, the probabilities become greater that a procedural "precedent" will apply, as Appellate Bodies continue to draw comparisons to previous panel decisions.

The U.S. also requested the changing of the test for decisions related to the "aim-and-effect" of a law impeding international trade. The Appellate Body did, in effect, bring this test back through developing a more comprehensive test using Article III Section 1 of the GATT. In developing their new test for national treatment and "aim-and-effect," the Court focused on the phrase "so as to afford protection."¹⁶⁹ The Appellate Body, in addition to these changes, broadened the scope of compliance required by Japan to many "competitive and substitutable" alcoholic beverages.¹⁷⁰ The Appellate Body otherwise agreed with the panel decision, and recommended that the DSB ask Japan to bring its laws into compliance with

168. *Id.* at sec. E.

169. *Id.* at sec. G.

170. See *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS11/AB/R, sec. F, available in 1996 WL 7338800 (Oct. 4, 1996).

GATT 1994.¹⁷¹ The Appellate Body report was circulated to Members on October 4, 1996.

D. Arbitration

Countries must comply with guidelines set out by the DSB immediately, within fifteen months, unless unusual circumstances exist in a given dispute. If an agreement is not reached within forty-five days, a party may request binding arbitration. The arbitrator is generally taken from the original panel, although they may also come from elsewhere. If the original parties do not agree upon a panelist then a party may request the DSB appoint an arbitrator. The Appellate Body recommends a period of time allowed for implementation of the decision within ninety days of issuance of the Appellate Report. The arbitration decision is binding, and neither party may request a second arbitration decision.¹⁷²

On November 20, 1996, Japan proposed to implement the DSU decision within a "reasonable time period." While the Japanese came to an agreement with the E.C., the U.S. determined that Japan's desires to gradually make change between two and five years constituted an unacceptable implementation. Consequently, the U.S. requested binding arbitration on December 24, 1996, and then requested that the Directorate-General appoint an arbitrator on January 7. Ten days later the Directorate-General selected the arbitrator, Julio Lacarte-Muro (Muro) to arbitrate the dispute.¹⁷³ Lacarte-Muro had been Presiding Member over the Appellate Body for this case.

The United States recommended a five month implementation of DSB recommendation because it felt Japan should be able to implement virtually immediately given that it was budget season. Japan countered that the measures were so severe that they would take time to implement because the magnitude of this change was unprecedented; the political system makes it difficult to establish quick change,

171. See *id.* at sec. 1.

172. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 21, paras. 1, 3-4.

173. See *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS11/13, paras. 1-11, available in 1997 WL 87372 (Feb. 14, 1997).

and; the consumers and distributors needed time to adjust, and this should be done gradually.¹⁷⁴ The U.S. countered that Japan stated in the past that it could change tax laws within six months, and further that five years is so long that it would undermine the credibility of the system.¹⁷⁵

The E.C. and Canada sat in as third parties, invited by the U.S. and Japan. The E.C. proposed fifteen months as an appropriate time for compliance. Canada pointed out that the periods suggested by Japan were not reasonable and that particular circumstances are unique to each case. Further, Canada argued that if the DSU allowed Japan five years to resolve such a practice, then it would be tantamount to arguing that the more inconsistent a measure is, the greater a period of time a Member should have to bring it into compliance.¹⁷⁶

On a related note, decisions such as this potentially have a great effect on what happens if a country like China has measures that stray far from compliance with GATT. It goes to the heart of the matter that if China were allowed more time to bring measures way out of synch into compliance with acceptable standards, then it could take a very long time for China to comply. If, however, China was forced to comply evenly then a much greater percentage of benefit or concession would accrue to other countries more quickly. In this instance, however, the arbitrator decided that Japan should adhere to a fifteen-month standard. Further, it was reemphasized that this law has power over local jurisdiction, and that lack of ability to enforce locally is no excuse for noncompliance.¹⁷⁷ The report was returned to the DSB on February 14, 1997.

IV. APPLICATION OF DISPUTE SETTLEMENT PROCESS TO WORLD SYSTEMS

Countries, in joining GATT then the WTO, agreed that free trade was the best way to expansion, growth and

174. See *id.* at paras. 17-24.

175. See *id.* at paras. 14-16.

176. See generally *id.*

177. See *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, WT/DS11/13, para. 27, available in 1997 WL 87372 (Feb. 14, 1997).

prosperity because it would allow more goods, services and information to flow across borders without barriers. The resultant growth and prosperity would then bring people together in this common purpose.

However, as countries develop freer trade, conflicts arise. These conflicts often center around timing of implementation of measures. There is disagreement about which products qualify for similar taxation and which should be afforded differential treatment. Further, while countries pursue the ideal of free markets in principle, economic and social actors within countries are not comfortable relinquishing protections afforded to them.

The WTO and GATT provide a basis for deciding international trade issues. However, there are two noteworthy difficulties with treaties such as GATT and WTO. First, they must be interpreted with regard to how their general laws and principles apply to specific cases. Second, they are not all-encompassing, leaving many specific issues uncovered.

Under GATT, neither of these difficulties were dealt with effectively. Countries were, in essence, not required to follow rulings because no binding arbitration process was available. Even rulings which were adopted did not constitute binding law on the parties to the extent that enforcement of decisions was a viable option. This problem was exacerbated by the fact that GATT did not include a strong executive branch.¹⁷⁸ In essence, GATT lacks the "teeth" necessary to enforce its decisions.

The WTO Dispute Settlement Understanding now effects and will continue to effect the world system even more in the future by giving the free trade body the "teeth" to make and enforce decisions regarding a framework for increasingly freer trade. Two added characteristics of the DSU system especially afford it this opportunity, binding arbitration and a stronger ability to withstand future legal scrutiny. In the section which follows these two changes will be explained further, and then applied to pending cases. The effect on world systems of their application will

178. Trade leaders of Members provide an executive branch by meetings, but they do not do this often enough to constitute a strong executive branch.

then be demonstrated.

A. Improvement 1: Binding Arbitration

As explained in earlier sections, when the DSB makes a decision through adopting a panel or Appellate Body report, this decision is binding on the parties involved. Parties agree to abide by these decisions, and to not take unilateral action thus potentially starting a trade war. However, this decision does not provide the specific timetable for implementing recommendations, nor does it provide suggestions on how to accomplish this. Finally, and perhaps most importantly, the DSB decision does not provide any definitive consequences for non-compliance. Such consequences are accomplished through binding arbitration.

If the parties to the dispute can agree upon a reasonable time period for implementation of suggestions then arbitration becomes unnecessary. If, however, the countries can not come to an agreement among themselves, then they may agree to a binding arbitration process. This arbitration could be accomplished in a manner so as to keep in mind the fifteen month implementation guideline. While "special circumstances" of a country can allow it to exceed this guideline, it is rare. This was evident in the case *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages* in that it did not allow special circumstances either based on Japan's claims that it was difficult to pass through local (Japanese) legislature or that the magnitude of change in such a short time period was unprecedented.¹⁷⁹ In this same case, the panel agreed with the claims of the U.S. that Japan had implemented changes quickly in the past and may thus accomplish it in the same manner. Finally, if a country finds that the offender is not following the arbitration decision then it may either request authorization to be compensated or suspend concessions.¹⁸⁰ These measures will serve to strengthen the international system by forcing countries to follow the primary principle of free trade that underpins the GATT and the WTO. A second improvement to the dispute settlement system also aids its functioning by providing the

179. See *supra* Part III and accompanying text.

180. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 22.

important characteristic of having decisions with a stronger and more professional legal footing.

B. Improvement 2: Ability to Withstand Future Legal Scrutiny

Under GATT, the legal doctrine that was developed was not entirely reliable because the system consisted of panelists who were often neither well-trained nor sufficiently familiar with the GATT and WTO doctrine. Some of their decisions did not bring the consistency to cases necessary to establish a legal "system," and some were of questionable legal quality.¹⁸¹

To be effective, WTO cases must be capable of withstanding future legal scrutiny. In fact, this is the best opportunity for contributing to the development of the system: cases that will withstand the test of time, and legal consistency. Further, in common law, cases like these require consistency of reasoning and quality to be able to guide future decisions.¹⁸² At the very least, the principle of *stare decisis* should guide the reasoning. This was previously observed in *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, where reference to a previous case (generally adopted or unadopted GATT decision) is referred to for its guiding legal reasoning for virtually every piece of the decision by the panel and the Appellate Body. As previously mentioned, the Appellate Body admitted that a legitimate expectation for consistency of legal reasoning is created by adopting the panel or Appellate Body report. Taken together, these decisions begin to form a coherent basis for WTO law.

The Appellate Body, itself consisting of "recognized experts" in GATT and WTO law and international trade, comprises a professional and independent review board. This is another significant factor in lending credibility to

181. See Weiler & Pan, *supra* note 42.

182. There are civil law elements as well. Civil law would provide for carrying out the intent of the framers of the laws, which would be interpreted more to the letter of the framers, and little broad-based power of development or improvisation, even within a narrow context, would be allowed. Since there are currently elements of both common and civil law in the dispute settlement system, standards for mixed review will be developed over time.

decisions taken. Opinions become more capable of withstanding scrutiny after the high standards brought to the independent legal reasoning by this group. Further, the Appellate Body is brought away from political influence in its decision-making because the DSB has its own Secretariat to which it is responsible rather than the WTO Director-General. While the panel has many members from which to choose, the Appellate Body has only seven members who are professionally and regularly committed to this process. This has the effect of bringing consistency to decisions because of the small number of panelists and their limited four-year terms. Finally, given the number of cases for review, the time frame appears to allow for the Appellate Body members to read panel arguments in a full and unprejudiced manner.¹⁸³

Finally, the DSU provides increased transparency allowing for a more robust decision. In being able to view the process in light of third-party involvement, as well as involvement of developing countries, the system is more effective in its goal of fairness.¹⁸⁴ While difficulties in transparency exist when cases are settled, it is decisions that make their way through the full process, such as *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*, that create legal doctrine for the future.¹⁸⁵ Up to this point, the dispute settlement process has served its purpose very well, and it is accordingly being used frequently, with a positive impact on opening the trading system.

183. See Weiler & Pan, *supra* note 42.

184. See DSU, *supra* note 6, arts. 10-16, 21, 25.

185. See FINAL ACT, *supra* note 6, APPENDIX 4, DECISION ON THE APPLICATION AND REVIEW OF THE UNDERSTANDING ON RULES AND PROCEDURES GOVERNING THE SETTLEMENT OF DISPUTES, 33 I.L.M. 1259 (1994) [hereinafter SETTLEMENT APPLICATION]. This transparency is especially important during the first period given that the Ministerial Conference will decide, after four years of WTO establishment, "whether to continue, modify or terminate such dispute settlement rules and procedures." *Id.* at 1260. Without an ability to see what has occurred, neither the Ministerial Conference, nor the public the Ministers ultimately represent, will be able to come to decision regarding the effectiveness of the DSU. This is particularly important since perceived effectiveness is an important underpinning for actually using the dispute settlement process.

C. Future Prospects

The dispute settlement system is increasingly being used for enforcing articles outlined in treaties, as well as for developing rulings concerning the gray areas not covered by treaties. The two improvements to the dispute settlement system mentioned above allow for countries to have faith that the DSU will accomplish enforcement and clarification.

Binding arbitration allows for enforcement of articles already in effect by treaty. One example of this is *Japan-Taxes on Alcoholic Beverages*. Japan had agreed to concessions by initially signing the contract and then a 1989 GATT decision sought conformance. However, compliance was not complete. The U.S., Canada and the E.C. together requested that Japan comply more fully. Japan eventually fulfilled this request. Ultimately, it was not the panel or Appellate Body decision that determined when to comply, but only binding arbitration. This arbitration supported the general fifteen-month guideline for implementation, and Japan will be required to report to the DSB on its progress.¹⁸⁶

In another case of enforcement, *United States-Restrictions on Import of Cotton and Man-Made Fibre Underwear*,¹⁸⁷ the DSU found in favor of Costa Rica by holding that import restrictions imposed by the United States on imports were not valid. Had the U.S. not complied, arbitration would have been necessary. Moreover, the fact that the U.S. did comply so quickly evidences the deterrent effect of the arbitration process because the U.S. may have preferred to comply quickly rather than having the matter brought before an arbitration board.

A more expansive example that may require the aid of arbitration is *India-Patent Protection for Pharmaceutical and Agricultural Chemical Products* (India Patent Protection).¹⁸⁸ In this case (which is currently beginning consultation stage), the E.C. and the United States complained

186. See DSU, *supra* note 6, art. 21, para. 6.

187. WT/DS24/R, available in 1996 WL 738823 (Nov. 8, 1996).

188. WT/DS79/R, available in 1998 WL 527064 (Aug. 24, 1998); See also WT/DS50/AB/R, available in 1997 WL 781259 (Dec. 19, 1997) (providing DSU Appellate Body decision).

that India has not complied with the agreement concerning Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS). The E.C. alleges India did not protect marketing of pharmaceuticals and chemicals and India did not have a valid internal forum for raising the issue of violations of patents, nor for resolving such complaints expeditiously. When a decision is eventually rendered by the panel or Appellate Body (if an agreement is not reached before the case is tried), there may be a requirement for India to alter its laws. If this is the case, then arbitration may be required to determine a fair time frame for India to implement these changes. Such a decision would be especially important given that the fifteen-month guideline for implementation in developed countries does not directly apply to developing countries. The discretion of the governing body will determine when implementation must actually occur. Arbitration would, in effect, underwrite the ability for the E.C. and the U.S. to benefit from the TRIPS, as was agreed at the time of signing, in a reasonable time frame.

Decisions that are able to stand up to legal scrutiny also play an important role in changing the dynamics of the international system through enforcement of decisions on parties under dispute regarding matters not specifically covered under the treaties, as well as for enforcing unpopular decisions. This is true because such rulings may need to be made under common law, which requires the rule of law to interpret *de facto* laws from existing disputes.¹⁸⁹ This effective adding of laws will be required for handling issues that arise, for example, under the Government Procurement Agreement, or technical agreements under GATT, where all specifics could not possibly be covered.

One instance of this is the combined case of *Japan-Measures Affecting Distribution Services*,¹⁹⁰ where the complainant charges that Japan violates access to its markets. However, this is not a Most Favored Nation issue of

189. See Weiler & Pan, *supra* note 42. As was mentioned in Professor Weiler's seminar, a longer-term common law may be created by the courts. See *id.* This often happens because the government has not, and may be unwilling to, develop specific laws regarding matters at hand. See *id.* An example of this is the US Supreme Court, under the US Common Law system, developing case law regarding disputes over abortion issues. See *id.*

190. WT/DS45.

differential treatment; local stores also have the same issue of shorter hours than in the U.S. market. Accordingly, to decide upon this in a lasting manner, the DSB may need to advise Japan on developing and applying specific law that does not currently exist.

Another case where a great deal of interpretation in area not ruled upon entirely is *Indonesia-Certain Measures Affecting the Automobile Industry*.¹⁹¹ This case questions whether Indonesia may continue pledging its resources to its national car company, and examines whether Indonesia may continue to violate the GATT's national treatment standards. These issues may require the DSU to apply *de facto* case law to the matter. Furthermore, this case law will have to stand up to a great deal of legal scrutiny because of its potential unpopular effects it may have on many Indonesians, including the son of the ruler.

Ultimately, the ability of the DSU to support the decision made by the Members of the WTO to support this multilateral dispute resolution process in favor of a more open and fair system will be supported by these new characteristics of the dispute settlement process. Provided the DSU, and particularly the Appellate Body is able to handle the volume of cases that will be requested,¹⁹² it will be an effective tool for dispute resolution. As the number of cases increase, there may be another incentive to adopt a common law common law regime for the adjudication of disputes between Members. It may be required that a subordinate dispute settlement body to the panel and Appellate Body be developed because all cases may not be able to be tried in a timely fashion. This subordinate system would need to rely on the decisions of the adopted reports. Under these conditions, general enforcement through arbitration and strong legal reasoning behind decisions would certainly be necessary to support this or another view of macro dispute resolution. The system has changed and will change more as governments rely increas-

191. WT/DS54/R, available in 1998 WL 375971 (July 2, 1998).

192. *Overview of the State-of-Play of WTO Disputes*, World Trade Organization, <<http://www.wto.org/wto/dispute/bulletin.htm>> (last visited Apr. 20, 1997). The article stated that the DSU has handled 61 matters and only 5 have been completed and 21 have settled. See *id.*

ingly on the DSU to settle their disputes and enforce their treaties.

It appears that the improvements to the system have left it well equipped to deal with challenging issues. The next step will be, through education regarding legal issues, preparing various actors for these tough issues to be decided in a constructive manner under DSU. Both the Secretariat and "information dispersion" based on technology will play roles in this education.

V. CONCLUSION

The DSU makes the WTO at once exciting, more transparent and enforceable. It is a mechanism which has allowed the WTO to become a "GATT with teeth." The Directorate-General of the WTO, Renato Ruggiero (Ruggiero), has made remarks in Korea to a business association regarding the benefits of DSU:

no review of the achievements of the WTO would be complete without mentioning the Dispute Settlement system, in many ways the central pillar of the multilateral trading system and the WTO's most individual contribution to the stability of the global economy. The new WTO system is at once stronger, more automatic and more credible than its GATT predecessor. This is reflected in the increased diversity of countries using it and in the tendency to resolve cases "out of court" before they get to the final decision-19 out of 71 cases so far. The system is working as intended-as a means above all for conciliation and for encouraging resolution of disputes, rather than just for making judgments. By reducing the scope for unilateral actions, it is also an important guarantee of fair trade for middle-sized exporting nations such as Korea.¹⁹³

Further, Ruggiero spoke in China about the opportunities for the use of the DSU were China to become Members:

Equally importantly [sic] [to policy rights and responsibilities], China will have recourse to a multilateral forum for discussing trade problems with its WTO partners and, if necessary, to a binding dispute settlement procedure if its rights are impaired. This greater level of security will

193. Renato Ruggiero. *The Future Path of the Multilateral Trading System*, <<http://www.wto.org/wto/Whats-new/seoul.htm>> (May 18, 1997).

benefit China immensely-encouraging even greater business confidence, and attracting even greater levels of investment.¹⁹⁴

In other words, the DSU is a powerful system offering many opportunities to its Members and to the world system at-large. The DSU will increasingly be relied upon to settle issues that could otherwise be considered outside its initial scope.

Effective case law has only begun to develop, and it will develop further as Members gain greater confidence in this system. Even the few countries which are not yet under this case law system, such as China and Russia, will likely become Members in the future, increasing its scope of decision to nearly the entire world of nation-states.

However, another strong force which may provide a challenge for the WTO DSU is how actors will work outside of the system. One example of this issue is businesses working informally to develop on their own. They have as much, or in many cases more, ability to affect the international commercial system than virtually any government. Not only is this power and influence generally recognized by governments and corporations, but even Mr. Ruggiero recognized this publicly, admitting that the world system is comprised of able actors outside of nation-states:

I am honoured to be here today and to address a few remarks to such a distinguished [business] audience on the subject of the World Trade Organization. It would be difficult, I think-anywhere in the world-to match the commercial decision-making power represented here today. What you decide in the conduct of your affairs as leaders of American business, and the influence you exert on political decisions worldwide, profoundly affects us all. This makes me especially aware of the opportunity I have been given to participate in your deliberations.¹⁹⁵

A force in the international system that is as strong as

194. See Renato Ruggiero, *China and the World Trading System*, <<http://www.wto.org/wto/Whats-new/chipress.htm>.> (last visited May 18, 1997).

195. Renato Ruggiero, *The Multilateral Trading System: American Vision and American Leadership*, <<http://www.wto.org/wto/Pressrel/press24.htm>.> (last visited May 16, 1997).

business should have formal forums for involvement. One option for giving forum to business is allowing it to exist behind the scenes with governments. For example, Rick Johnson explained that these entities do gain forum through their government.¹⁹⁶ For example, the government makes available the briefs it submits to the Dispute Settlement Body. In developing these documents, the government allows the corporations to file *amicus* briefs to the government, to have their issues heard and understood in the final government draft.¹⁹⁷

An example of business having influence is found in the case concerning *Japan-Measures Affecting Consumer Photographic Film and Paper*,¹⁹⁸ where a panel has been established. This is an example of specific business interests in WTO DSU affairs; a long-standing dispute regarding Kodak's inability to penetrate the Japanese market has, perhaps, helped to bring this dispute. However, most of the work of business is accomplished outside the DSU system, and it is particularly difficult to classify a multi-national enterprise (MNE) as part of one nation-state and, therefore, related to one government.

Even governments often work outside the system. The panel in *United States-The Cuban Liberty and Solidarity Act* has been suspended, and without the real reasons necessarily being brought to light.¹⁹⁹ Perhaps the system simply worked too well for them to want to work inside of it. Both may have been afraid of what might happen had a binding decision been reached. Ms. Amelia Porges, Senior Counsel for Dispute Settlement at the Office of the U.S. Trade Representative, pointed out that the dispute settlement system "needs to deliver certainty, not a zig-zag . . . since it is expensive and painful when government needs to change plans."²⁰⁰ A decision by the panel regarding this issue would be an uncertainty-and a "loss"

196. Phone Interview with Richard A. Johnson, Senior Partner, Arnold & Porter, May 1, 1997 [hereinafter Johnson Interview].

197. See Ruggiero, *supra* note 123.

198. WT/DS44, available in 1998 WL 268878 (Mar. 3, 1998).

199. WT/DS38/5, available in 1997 WL 371060 (1997).

200. Phone Interview with Amelia Porges, Senior Counsel, Office of the U.S. Trade Representative (May 1, 1997) [hereinafter Porges interview].

for the United States would certainly force it to change plans.

Thus, an important challenge is how to get the governments for whom this system was intended to work out issues within the process.²⁰¹ Issues like these will arise and must be addressed. In a society balancing competition with integration and community, the principles of fairness of information movement and transparency allow the system a measure of sustainability. The multilateral system will help to lend this transparency to the international system.

Harlan Cleveland pointed out that a cocktail of "Hope and Fear" is a necessary ingredient for the success of an international organization (or regime). Ultimately, hope can be found in many places. One form of hope is embodied in organizations like the World Trade Organization. The WTO's Dispute Settlement Understanding mechanism will encourage a secure environment for business and global citizens. Fear can also be found. The multilateral system could break down, as many of its previous bodies are not willing to acquiesce to an "uncentralized,"²⁰² world and so become increasingly irrelevant.²⁰³

One solution for balancing centralization and uncentralization is keeping an openness to differences. As uncentralization occurs, this will be required for communication between the many smaller authorities that occur.

201. This points to a wisdom of having conciliation as the primary stage in the negotiation—neither side risks too much, both in terms of "losing face" and negative outcome. Of course, engagement is more likely under these conditions.

202. See CLEVELAND, *supra* note 2, at 30-64. "Uncentralized" is a concept which is like decentralization of power in that decisions are dispersed. However, in decentralization authority ultimately rests with a central authority. However, with uncentralization power itself is dispersed, and there is no authority strong enough to hold central power over these many smaller bodies. A story was told demonstrating uncentralization:

A young army captain is passing his battalion in review under the critical eye of a senior general. The battalion commander gives his order in a conversational tone of voice: "Battalion march." The visiting dignitary leans over to give a word of advice: "Young man, you have to shout the order, so they all start at once." The captain looks back tolerantly at this relic of the age of administrative pyramids. "It's all right, General," he replies. "The word will get around." Technology is the largest cause of the move from the decentralized to the uncentralized model. Information and knowledge are power, and they are being dispersed rapidly by the Internet and many other information networks. See *id.*, at 30-64.

203. See CLEVELAND, *supra* note 2, at 58-64.

Differences in income and culture give rise to disputes, such as the issues of North and South, or Eastern or Fundamentalist Cultures which each pose challenging issues to the West. These issues could use a forum, such as the DSU, which transcends national boundaries. If the DSU is able to maintain its goals of promoting free trade, increased general openness; and "Equal [or "National"] Treatment," then the DSU may develop into this forum.²⁰⁴

204. See Johnson Interview, *supra* note 196.